
Ranking of the environmental sustainability of Cuban provinces using a non-compensatory multi-criteria model

Abstract:

Environmental sustainability has evolved to become a multidimensional concept, applied to diverse fields of study, to ensure the balance between society and the environment. Among the initiatives for its application, composite indicators have been proposed as one of the options for the management and protection of natural resources. Cuba, with the updating of its economic and social model, has progressively advanced in these aspects, but there is still a lack of knowledge necessary to promote greater involvement in the processing of environmental statistical information and work with composite indicators.

In the present work, a proposal for a composite indicator for the evaluation of sustainability at the provincial level was made to facilitate the interpretation of the information by the stakeholders and policy makers. The construction of the composite indicator was carried out using a non-compensatory procedure computed by a mixed-integer linear programming model.

Keywords: Environmental sustainability; [composite](#) indicator; [MCDM techniques](#); non-compensatory procedure; Cuba

1 Introduction

One of the main challenges facing the world's economies today is to mitigate environmental degradation amidst the desperate desire for economic growth (De Alcântara et al., 2015; Sarache-Castro, 2015; Scur & Heinz, 2016). To reduce pollution and contribute to sustainability, countries around the world are committed to minimising the adverse effects of climate change. Consistent with Agenda 21, the United Nations Commission on Sustainable Development has developed a set of indicators covering several of the dimensions of sustainability which has become more relevant today (Saint et al., 2019). This concept applies to the global and regional context, where Latin American and Caribbean countries are suffering the adverse impacts of climate change with the manifestation of phenomena such as increased water scarcity, increased flooding and sea level rise, and other negative consequences.

Cuba is not isolated from this reality, as the guidelines for sustainable development have become one of the priorities of Cuban state policy for the conservation of its natural resources, using statistical information to assess the state of the environment and its impacts.

National policies addressing the environment are based on the programmatic documents of the Cuban social project, the National Environmental Strategy (EAN) and Decree Law 281, 2007: Government Information System. In the case of the EAN, this has had four cycles of

formulation and implementation: from 1997 to the current 2016-2020 cycle. These documents constitute the pillars for the planning of the country's environmental policies based on existing environmental indicators which make it possible to evaluate, communicate and improve environmental management.

In matters of environmental sustainability, indicators are evaluation tools that allow analysing and checking the success of selected actions and policies, and whether they are acting appropriately on the path towards sustainable development (Bank, 1997; Bell & Morse, 2008; Farsari & Prastacos, 2002; Hardi & Barg, 1997; Pintér et al., 2005).

As various international organisations consider many of the indicators measured in Cuba for the calculation of composite indicators (CI) of environmental sustainability, it is important to promote their use in the country for decision-making by means of a proposal that enables the parties involved to monitor them in order to draw up local policies.

The CI complements a panel of simple indicators. It in no way removes their usefulness, but rather provides a global vision of the phenomenon to be investigated. As a synthetic measure of environmental sustainability, its importance lies in the fact that more management information can be integrated, aspects that cannot be captured by a simple indicator can be considered together, it facilitates understanding for all users and permits decisions to be made between different areas, whether at local, country, continental or global level, depending on the scope of the information.

2 Objective and structure of the article

The general objective of this research is to develop a proposal that enables the analysis of environmental sustainability by means of a composite indicator as a support for local decision-making and the projection of national policies on environmental care.

This article is divided into two parts. First, proposals for CI of environmental sustainability and their application framework are discussed. Subsequently, the CI is proposed, using a non-compensatory multi-criteria model for its application in Cuba.

3 Composite indicators of environmental sustainability

3.1. Environmental dimension of sustainability. Measurement in Cuba.

The term sustainable development is mentioned for the first time in the World Conservation Strategy (1980) (Soler, 2018). It was also brought up in the 1987 Report Our Common Future, defined as "development that meets the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs". (WCED, 1987).

Since the first use of this concept, numerous studies have been published on sustainability, from different perspectives, always conceiving it as a desirable objective for balanced development (Martínez-Vega et al., 2016).

Sustainability is managed at different levels of time and space in different organisational contexts. Basically, encompassing three dimensions or pillars (economic, social and environmental), it can be applied in economic sectors, countries, municipalities, neighbourhoods, goods and services (Blancas et al., 2018; Kourtit et al., 2020; Mahdi Mousavi & Lin, 2020; Munda, 2012a; Pérez et al., 2017). In this sense, several authors agree that sustainability, from an environmental point of view, refers to the capacity to maintain biological aspects in their productivity and diversity over time, to preserve natural resources and to foster a conscious ecological responsibility (Guijarro, 2019; Hamadeh et al., 2017; Jafari et al., 2018; João et al., 2018; Lehmann et al., 2020; Luzzati & Gucciardi, 2015; Pang et al., 2018; Saud et al., 2020).

This requires a reorientation and restructuring of institutions towards global management, considering not only environmental sustainability, but also economic and governance issues.

Among the main tools for measuring sustainability are indicators. Indicators can be used directly, providing valuable information to the decision-making process. **In this regard, an aggregated measure of the values of a set of indicators may provide a good explanatory index, since composite indicators, when created with the minimum loss of information, help to reduce the size of a set of indicators allowing the measurement of multidimensional concepts which cannot be captured by a single indicator (Nardo et al., 2005a).**

In this sense, Eustachio et al. (2019) argue that, although the use of indicators is widely used to measure sustainability, there are monitoring issues that create a gap between the establishment of control mechanisms with efficient feedback channels and the use of indicators to measure sustainability:

- Sustainability is only measured by adopting a few variables at a time or by a one-dimensional indicator.
- The knowledge between governance processes and the use of such indicators has not been deeply addressed by the literature.

Since 2000, progress has been made in the international arena in the development of a set of sustainable development indicators. Institutions such as the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) have developed or strengthened their environmental indicators related to sustainable development (OECD, 2000, 2003, 2008). Following these guidelines, the countries of Latin America and the Caribbean are joining together their will to implement environmental and sustainable development indicators, presenting initiatives that include different scales and methodological approaches.

For its part, the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) has synthesised, through various publications, those

proposals relevant to Latin American and Caribbean countries, highlighting those on a national scale which show technical quality and communication power, or which are presented in suggestive frameworks. Systems of indicators made up of different areas and dimensions are reviewed, which, as a whole, show the main environmental or sustainable development trends in the respective countries. In addition, some aggregate indicators (index type) are also considered that could be useful for the countries of the region (CEPAL, 2018). In these countries, technical and financial obstacles prevail that hinder their systematic development. One of them is the need for stable official environmental statistical series to facilitate the calculation and updating of environmental indicators. (Bell & Morse, 2008).

In the case of Cuba, in line with the Millennium Development Goals, the state recognises the need to guarantee environmental sustainability, proposing as a goal the incorporation of the principles of sustainable development in national policies and programmes and investing in the conservation of natural resources. To this end, statistics are published periodically in various fields showing a set of indicators, as a quantitative measure expressing compliance with legal requirements, environmental objectives and international commitments that guide decision-making (Espino et al., 2015; Martínez, 2006; Mateo, 2008).

Rodríguez et al. (2018) states that: “although the political intention of the Cuban state is to achieve sustainable development, the territorial approach that aims at local development in accordance with the natural resources of each region is still limited” (p. 733). It is therefore essential for the country to have a single measure based on simple data (indicators), which would support initiatives such as the Life Task, planned by the Ministry of Science, Technology and Environment (CITMA), to tackle climate change.

Actions aimed at contributing to environmental sustainability are reflected in the Constitution of the Republic of Cuba. Together with some concrete actions for sanitation, recycling and reforestation, laws have been established to regulate environmental protection and the sustainable use of resources. Among the most relevant legislative proposals related to the environment, following the mention of the concept of sustainable development in the Bruntland Report and the Rio Summit of 1992, the following can be mentioned (Rodríguez & Peña Fuentes, 2019):

- ✓ 1992: Article 27 of the Constitution of the Republic is amended, strengthening the idea of integrating the environment into sustainable social and economic development.
- ✓ 1993: Approval of the National Environment and Development Programme (Cuban adaptation of Agenda 21).
- ✓ 1994: Creation of the Ministry of Science, Technology and Environment (CITMA), the governing body for environmental policy. Considered the Central State Administration Agency (OACE); it develops strategies and actions to maintain the environmental achievements attained.

- ✓ 1995: The National Environmental Strategy and the National Commission for the Protection of the Environment and Conservation of Natural Resources are created.
- ✓ 1997: Law 81 of the Environment, the core of the environmental legal framework in Cuba, is published in the Official Gazette of the Republic of Cuba.
- ✓ 2000: Decree-Law No. 2012 on Coastal Zone Management is implemented with the aim of implementing the General Plan for Territorial and Urban Planning in coastal areas.
- ✓ 2017: The Life Task was approved. This is the State Plan for Confronting Climate Change, made up of 11 tasks divided into 5 strategic lines to develop actions based on diagnoses of danger, vulnerability and environmental risk in vulnerable areas of the archipelago.
- ✓ 2019: A new Constitution of the Republic of Cuba is approved, from which complementary legal regulations on environmental protection are derived.

In a report on the discrepancies in the indicators for meeting the Millennium Development Goals, with regard to Goal 7: "ensure environmental sustainability", which is part of ECLAC's statistical publications, Taccari & Stockins (2014) identify the difficulty Cuba has in aligning its statistical information with international reports due to the lack of tools to account for the information. This means that there is little information on the behaviour of environmental sustainability to be included in the international database. Another limitation for obtaining statistical information is that the country does not have an environmental statement of accounts. (CEPAL, 2017).

*3.2 Bibliographic analysis of **composite** indicators for measuring environmental sustainability*

One of the most commonly used definitions of a synthetic or composite indicator (**CI**) is the one proposed by Pena, which defines it as: "that mathematical function of the partial indicators that brings together a set of conditions deemed necessary to achieve an expressive measurement of the objective pursued" (Pena, 1978; p. 25).

The main characteristic of **CI**s is the ability to condense information from complex and dynamic environments which need to be simplified and analysed, making them ideal for measuring multidimensional concepts such as sustainability, which are difficult to capture in a simple indicator. In other words, **CI**s contribute to a better interpretation of information than looking for a common behaviour in a set of individual indicators (Abenayake et al., 2018; Burgass et al., 2017; Lozano-Oyola et al., 2019; Luzzati & Gucciardi, 2015; Munda, 2012a; Munda & Nardo, 2009; Nardo et al., 2005a; Nardo et al., 2005b; Pérez et al., 2013; Rogge, 2018). They may include quantitative, qualitative or a combination of quantitative and qualitative indicators.

Table 1 shows a sample of the proposed composite indicators for environmental sustainability, according to the bibliography consulted in chronological order, which includes initiatives by international organisations and various researchers in the field.

Each CI was developed using different aggregation methods, variables and approaches. In terms of scale, various units have been used: national, regional, provincial and local. The composite indicators, ICES and EPI, use some simple indicators in common, such as infant mortality, marine protected areas, access to safe drinking water and access to sanitation.

For example, the authors Oțoiu & Grădinaru (2018) propose an alternative to the Environmental Performance Index (EPI) by constructing a proof-of-concept index based on component variables whose changes reflect the actual state of the environment and environmental sustainability in the particular dimensions measured. These authors also propose changes to the Environmental Status and Sustainability Index (ESSI) by taking into account the relationships between the variables when constructing the composite index, verifying the relevance of the theoretical environmental dimensions compared to the factor components. This explains the complex relationships between the environmental variables and aims to achieve a weighting of the component variables. Regarding the simple indicators selected in each case, some are repeated, especially those used by international organisations. Others differ from one study to another, depending on their objective and the needs of decision-makers. There are also differences in their mathematical expression, the type of indicator and its combination (qualitative or quantitative), or in the sources of information used.

Table 1: Presentation of composite indicators of environmental sustainability based on the literature review.

Reference	Name and field of application	Number of simple indicators	Normalization method	Aggregation Method
Edmonds et al. (2020)	Composite indicator of vulnerability to climate change (<i>CCVI</i>). Applied to compare countries.	6	Yes	Data Envelopment Analysis (<i>DEA</i>)
Grima & Singh (2020)	Ecosystem Services Potential Indicator (<i>ESPI</i>). Applicable to Caribbean countries.	5	No	Boundary Point Distance
Ho et al. (2019)	Subjective Environmental Vulnerability Index based on Neighbourhood. Estimates the environmental health of a community.	8	Yes	Principal Component Analysis with Varimax rotation
Moghim & Garna (2019)	Environmental Resilience Indicator (<i>ERI</i>). It is used in the comparison between countries.	6	Yes	Linear Regression
Mohsin et al. (2019)	Composite indicator of energy security and environmental sustainability. Used in countries with the highest greenhouse gas emissions.	13	Yes	Data Envelopment Analysis (<i>DEA</i>)
Saint et al. (2019)	Proposed <i>CI</i> based on a globalisation indicator. It is used for the city level.	4	No	Linear Regression
Shah et al. (2019)	Energy Security and Environmental Sustainability Index (<i>ESESI</i>). Used in countries.	11	No	Data Envelopment Analysis (<i>DEA</i>)
Abenayake et al. (2018)	Composite indicator to assess community resilience to flooding.	13	Yes	Linear Aggregation
Dialga (2018)	Sustainability Index for Mining Countries (<i>SIMC</i>). Applied to countries with large mining resources.	6	Yes	Geometric Aggregation
Martínez-Vega et al. (2016)	Composite indicator of forestry sustainability of forestry in Spain. Provincial scale.	20	Yes	Average of the indices relating to each of the

				dimensions of sustainability
García-Sánchez et al. (2015)	Composite Environmental Performance Indicator (<i>CIEP</i>). Used in countries.	19	Yes	Linear Aggregation in two steps.
(Hsu et al., 2014)	Composite Environmental Performance Indicator (<i>EPI</i>). Applied to countries.	22	Yes	Linear Aggregation in three steps
Pinar et al. (2014)	Environmental Sustainability Indicator of the <i>FEEM</i> (<i>Fondazione Eni Enrico Mattei</i>). Applied to countries.	19	Yes	Equal Weight for Each Indicator
Pert et al. (2012)	Composite indicator for monitoring vegetation condition. Regional scope	8	No	Summing the value for each indicator
Giannetti et al. (2009)	Environmental Sustainability Indicator (<i>ESI</i>). Implemented in countries.	21	Yes	Simple Additive Weighting
Lasso de la Vega & Urrutia (2001)	Pollution-Sensitive Human Development Index (<i>HDPI</i>). Applicable to countries.	3	No	Adding the value for each indicator
WWF (1998)	Living Planet Index (<i>LPI</i>). Applicable to terrestrial, freshwater and marine ecosystems.	1100	No	Geometric Mean
Wackernagel & Rees (1997)	Ecological Footprint (<i>EF</i>). It is based on the quantitative requirements of land and water to maintain a certain standard of living. Applicable to countries, regions and cities.	Arbitrary	Yes	Adding the value for each indicator

Source: Own elaboration.

4 Construction of a composite indicator of environmental sustainability. Application in Cuban provinces.

In order to construct a **CI**, certain guidelines must be followed to find the components and sub-components that are needed based on theoretical studies, empirical and intuitive analysis by the researcher, or a combination of these elements. Three stages are used to construct the **CI**: **Selection of simple indicators, normalization and aggregation procedure**. In this case, because of the aggregation procedure, we will see that the normalization process will be not required.

4.1 Selection of simple indicators

Despite the existence of various sets of composite indicators for measuring environmental sustainability at different levels, there is no academic consensus on a universal list of simple indicators for measuring environmental sustainability, nor an ideal number of simple indicators. There is agreement that the selection of indicators should be made in a way that represents the needs of decision-makers and other stakeholders (Lozano-Oyola et al., 2019; Pérez et al., 2016).

Regarding the available information, the National Office of Statistics and Information of Cuba (*ONEI*), subordinated to the Ministry of Communications, is in charge of compiling information that permits knowing the behaviour of economic, demographic and social processes. As the governing body for statistics at the national level, it establishes the rules for its organisation and operation. Its statistical yearbooks collect information on the following variables: territory, population, institutional organisation, national accounts, finances, employment and salaries, economic performance in terms of imports and exports, production lines, education, sport, health and the environment.

With respect to environmental statistics, this institution issues indicators that show the situation in this area in the country and the steps it has taken to join the international effort to know and study the environmental reality. This enables the formulation and implementation of sustainable development practices.

At a general level, there is no universally accepted list of environmental sustainability indicators, although general criteria have been given for selecting them depending on how they relate to the concept, definitions and dimensions of sustainability, as well as the availability of information and expert judgement concerning their usefulness (Martínez-Vega et al., 2016).

The criteria followed to select the indicators to be included in the proposed **CI** were the usefulness and availability of the statistical information, and the frequency with which it is used, as stated by the authors Lozano-Oyola et al. (2019), Mohsin et al. (2019) and Pert et al. (2012). Given that the objective of this research is to propose a tool for provincial management, 10 indicators were used to cover this scope:

- Drinking water coverage

- Sanitation coverage
- Area planted with trees
- Proportion forest cover
- Area set aside for protected areas
- Area damaged by forest fires
- Economic losses due to forest fires
- Volume of solid waste collected
- Investment expenditure for environmental protection
- Pollution load

For each of them, a panel was constructed for the years 2011 and 2018 for the 16 units or alternatives (15 provinces and the special municipality Isla de la Juventud), with the objective of carrying out a comparative analysis in the visualisation of results. **A statistical summary of the indicators (mean and standar desviation-STD) is shown in the following table:**

Table 2: Indicators included on the study.

Indicator	Sign	Mean 2015	Mean 2018	STD 2015	STD 2018	Measurement units
Drinking water coverage	Positive	95.987	93.106	7.973	10.127	%
Sanitation coverage	Positive	97.548	94.915	5.553	8.994	%
Area planted with trees	Positive	0.164	0.496	0.129	0.243	%
Proportion forest cover	Positive	25.977	21.624	28.532	22.299	%
Area set aside for protected areas	Negative	6.250	6.250	19.492	10.771	%
Area damaged by forest fires	Negative	0.035	0.208	0.100	0.271	%
Economic losses due to forest fires	Negative	2.730	2.069	1.419	0.940	%
Volume of solid waste collected	Positive	6.250	6.250	8.072	10.552	m ³ /inhabitant
Investment expenditure for environmental protection	Negative	6.250	6.250	3.191	3.299	%
Pollution load	Positive	31.506	28.744	14.450	15.421	% of ton Biological Oxygen Demand/year

Source: Own elaboration

4.2 *Weighting and aggregation procedure*

A non-compensatory multi-criteria model was chosen for the aggregation of the indicators proposed in Munda & Nardo (2009) and later applied in Munda (2012a, 2012b, 2014, 2015) and Munda & Saisana (2011), among others **comprising non-compensatory methods** (Attardi et al. 2018; Cabello, 201; Greco et al. 2020; Mazziotta and Pareto 2016). In a similar way, other authors proposed novel procedures which permits to modulate the degree of compensation between indicators. See, for instance, the proposals developed in Ruiz et al. (2011) and Cabello et al. (2014).

Although these family of procedures maintains the main characteristics of an aggregation procedure, the final objective is the construction of a ranking of the set of alternatives, through the construction of a CI. The mathematical procedure is composed of two main steps. Firstly, a pair-wise comparison of alternatives according to each of the individual indicators is carried out. In a second stage, a complete pre-order of alternatives is formed, induced based on the weighted values of the pair-wise comparisons.

The procedure finally selected in this paper is justified because the addressed topic and the feasibility for proposing future strategies. Since the target of the CI is the measurement of the environmental sustainability, we consider that compensation between individual factors is not desirable, that is, a potential trade-off between any of the individual indicators does not reflect a correct approach to this topic.

In addition, the proposed procedure based of the model developed in Lozano et al. (2019) includes a post optimization analysis that would permit the development of improvement strategies individualized for each alternative.

Let us consider a set of N alternatives (provinces) to be evaluated with respect to K individual indicators. We denote by I_{ik} the values of alternative i ($i = 1, \dots, N$) with respect to indicator k ($k = 1, \dots, K$). An $N \times N$ matrix (denoted by E) can be constructed by comparing the elements I_{ik} for $i \neq j$. Each element of the matrix e_{ij} ($i \neq j$) is the result of the pair-wise comparisons according to the K individual indicators between provinces i and j . A global comparison can be determined by computing the following value,

$$e_{ij} = \sum_{k=1}^K (w_k(\text{Pr}_{ij}) + \frac{1}{2} w_k(\text{In}_{ij})) \quad (1)$$

where $w_k(\text{Pr}_{ij})$ and $w_k(\text{In}_{ij})$ are the weights of indicator k presenting, respectively, a preference and indifference relation between provinces i and j . The equality $e_{ij} + e_{ji} = 1$ clearly holds.

It is important to bear in mind how the values are assigned to the values e_{ij} . We consider that the weighting vector w has been obtained by an external process. In the pairwise comparison process, the values of each individual indicator are considered separately. That is, for an individual indicator k , if province i is preferred to province j , then the corresponding value w_k is assigned to i and nothing is assigned to j . **If the values for both alternatives coincide** (I_{ik} and I_{jk} are the equal) then half of the value of w_k is assigned to both provinces. The value of e_{ij} is computed as the sum of all

the comparisons of alternative i with respect to the remaining $n - 1$ alternatives.

To determine the best ranking, an adaptation of the maximum-likelihood ranking is developed. Let us denote by $R = \{r_s\}, s = (1, 2, \dots, N!)$ the set of all possible complete rankings that can be constructed for the set of alternatives. For each ranking r_s , the score corresponding to that ranking will be the sum of the e_{ik} values that represent it. Thus, this score is determined as:

$$\phi_s = \sum e_{ij}, \text{ where } i \neq j, e_{ij} \in r_s. \quad (2)$$

We therefore seek to determine the order that maximises the value ϕ_r . To this end, we apply the methodology developed in Loyola et al. (2019) in which the optimal value of the ranking is determined by solving a mixed-integer linear programming model.

This methodology enables the weights to be used as coefficients of importance, thus eliminating the compensatory nature in the construction of the indicators. In other words, a good or excellent performance in one indicator does not compensate for a poor performance in another. This makes it interesting in contexts in which economic and environmental indicators are dealt with simultaneously, so as not to allow trade-offs of one for the other, as in the case of indicators related to environmental pollution compensated by economic indicators (more pollution can be caused because favourable economic results compensate for it, which favours the position in the ranking).

Another advantage is that it does not require a process of normalisation of the indicators, as it uses ordinal values in terms of preference, which makes the process less subjective. On the other hand, it has several limitations, such as the technique used to adjust the scales and the determination of the corresponding weights for each initial indicator. In addition, by using information from ordinal indicators, the intensity of preference shown by the absolute values of these indicators is lost, which is a drawback in exchange for reduced compensability. This limitation can be overcome by introducing preference and indifference thresholds during the paired comparisons. (Pérez et al., 2017) .

4.3 Results

The application of the proposed method made it possible to obtain a ranking of the Cuban provinces for 2011 and another for 2018, where the value 1 is associated with the best alternative or position in the ranking and 16 with the worst. The calculation process was carried out with a programme based on the General Algebraic Modeling System computer language (GAMS). Ten pairwise comparison matrices were constructed for each year. From these individual binary matrices as well as from the E-weighted matrix, information on the performance of the provinces can already be obtained (Table 3). Values higher than 0.5 represent a better performance of the alternative.

Table 3: Weighted pairwise comparison matrix ¹.

	PR	AR	LH	MAY	MAT	VC	C	SS	CA	CAM	LT	H	G	SC	GUA	IJ
PR		0.65	0.60	0.60	0.40	0.50	0.65	0.55	0.50	0.50	0.60	0.60	0.55	0.50	0.35	0.20
AR	0.35		0.45	0.45	0.45	0.25	0.55	0.35	0.30	0.15	0.55	0.60	0.25	0.20	0.15	0.25
LH	0.40	0.55		0.50	0.50	0.50	0.65	0.45	0.40	0.50	0.50	0.60	0.45	0.30	0.25	0.40
MAY	0.40	0.55	0.50		0.60	0.60	0.45	0.55	0.60	0.50	0.50	0.60	0.45	0.40	0.25	0.40
MAT	0.60	0.55	0.50	0.40		0.40	0.45	0.55	0.50	0.40	0.40	0.60	0.45	0.40	0.45	0.30
VC	0.50	0.75	0.50	0.40	0.60		0.45	0.55	0.40	0.40	0.60	0.70	0.35	0.40	0.35	0.40
C	0.35	0.45	0.35	0.55	0.55	0.55		0.45	0.30	0.45	0.55	0.50	0.55	0.30	0.15	0.35
SS	0.45	0.65	0.55	0.45	0.45	0.45	0.55		0.40	0.55	0.65	0.70	0.45	0.50	0.45	0.35
CA	0.50	0.70	0.60	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.70	0.60		0.50	0.60	0.60	0.50	0.60	0.50	0.30
CAM	0.50	0.85	0.50	0.50	0.60	0.60	0.55	0.45	0.50		0.60	0.70	0.25	0.50	0.35	0.30
LT	0.40	0.45	0.50	0.50	0.60	0.40	0.45	0.35	0.40	0.40		0.60	0.35	0.40	0.35	0.30
H	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.40	0.30	0.50	0.30	0.40	0.30	0.40		0.40	0.40	0.20	0.20
G	0.45	0.75	0.55	0.55	0.55	0.65	0.45	0.55	0.50	0.75	0.65	0.60		0.50	0.25	0.35
SC	0.50	0.80	0.70	0.60	0.60	0.60	0.70	0.50	0.40	0.50	0.60	0.60	0.50		0.30	0.40
GUA	0.65	0.85	0.75	0.75	0.55	0.65	0.85	0.55	0.50	0.65	0.65	0.80	0.75	0.70		0.35
IJ	0.80	0.75	0.60	0.60	0.70	0.60	0.65	0.65	0.70	0.70	0.70	0.80	0.65	0.60	0.65	

Source: Own elaboration.

For example, if we compare PR vs AR, we see that Pinar wins by 0.65 vs 0.35. In a very simplified way, it wins in indicators that represent 65% of the total importance of the system. In this case, a uniform and normalised vector was considered which contained all the values, since in this research there is no external information provided by decision-makers. For this step, some authors mention the use of other methodologies such as Delphi or AHP to identify or search for a vector that represents the relative importance of the system (Domínguez Serrano et al., 2011; González, 2011; Lozano-Oyola et al., 2019; Pérez et al., 2017). This table also permits us to identify the strengths and weaknesses of each alternative, locating which alternatives are the best rated and which will provide the highest level of plausibility in the order.

The way in which composite indicators are presented is not a trivial matter, as they should facilitate communication to decision-makers and other end-users quickly and accurately. In particular, the graphical representation of composite indicators should provide clear messages, without obscuring individual data points. On the other hand, visual presentations can provide extremely sensitive signals from the user's perspective, e.g., problem areas requiring policy intervention, etc., and are therefore very useful. There are interesting ways of displaying and visualising composite indicators from simple tabular tools to more complicated multidimensional graphs (Nardo et al., 2005b). The resulting arrangement is shown in Figure 1 below.

¹ Note: The acronym notation for the provinces or units of comparison is: PR: Pinar del Río, AR: Artemisa, LH: La Habana, MAY: Mayabeque, MAT: Matanzas, VC: Villa Clara, C: Cienfuegos, SS: Sancti Spiritus, CA: Ciego de Ávila, CAM: Camagüey, LT: Las Tunas, H: Holguín, G: Granma, SC: Santiago de Cuba, GUA: Guantánamo, IJ: Special municipality Isla de la Juventud.

In total, the model evaluates all the possible orders of the 16 provinces and selects the one with the highest value of these sums, called Likelihood value (likelihood coefficient). Its calculation is based on the order of alternatives that has the highest support or stability measured in two-by-two preferences; i.e., it calculates the sum of the pairwise preference values. The likelihood coefficients are equal to 44.35 for the 2011 ranking and 77.6 for the 2018 ranking.

Figure 1: Ranking obtained for 2011 and 2018. Source: Own elaboration.

In 2011 the province with the best overall performance was Pinar del Río, and in 2018 Isla de la Juventud. In the worst positions for 2011 and 2018 were Artemisa and Holguín, respectively. Overall, in 2018 compared to 2011, 6 provinces improved, 8 worsened and 2 remained in the same position (Cienfuegos and Guantánamo).

Composite indicators provide a starting point for analysis. While they can be used as summary indicators to guide policy and data work, they can also be decomposed so that the contribution of individual sub-components and indicators can be identified, and the analysis of a country's performance can be expanded. This analysis is referred to as "back to the details" (Nardo et al., 2005b). This allows for a more detailed analysis of the positions obtained by each unit.

For 2011, the top four provinces in the ranking are Pinar del Río, Guantánamo, Santiago de Cuba and Granma. Analysing the behaviour of the average of the indicators with respect to the global average, they are higher in the coverage of drinking water, the area planted with trees, the area allocated to protected areas, the proportion covered by forests, the pollution load and the investment expenditure for the protection of the environment. They perform below average in sanitation coverage, economic losses due to forest fires, area damaged by forest fires and volume of solid waste collected.

Performing the same analysis for 2018, in the top four places are Isla de la Juventud, Guantánamo, Pinar del Río and Ciego de Ávila. They perform favourably in drinking water coverage, area planted with trees, area allocated to protected areas, volume of solid waste collected, pollution load and proportion covered by forests. In sanitation coverage, economic losses due to forest fires, area damaged by forest fires and investment expenditures for environmental protection they show an average value below the global average.

5. Conclusions

The proposed **CI** contributes to the measurement of environmental sustainability in the Cuban provinces, taking as a basis simple indicators that constitute environmental statistics published by the competent body of the country under study. The aggregation process was carried out using a non-compensatory linear multi-criteria model which facilitates the comparison of units considering indicators with different units of measurement, which makes the procedure very useful.

The proposed procedure enables not only the elaboration of a final order that gives an idea of the behaviour of each alternative, also the fact that the result is obtained as a ranking through a linear model with integer variables

permits some questions of interest to be solved without too much effort. Thus, the thresholds of change of individual indicators in which one is interested and the necessary increase in a certain value for the alternative to improve its position in the final order or the sensitivity of the result with respect to a change in the vector of weights used can be studied. This analysis allows not only checking the stability of the result, but also studying which improvement strategies should be proposed for each alternative, identifying weaknesses and strengths in each case.

It is recognised that there is still a long way to go in Cuba in terms of searching for and visualising information, as well as in the inclusion of other indicators that, due to a lack of information, were not taken into account. Therefore, although it presents this weakness, it is a first step in the development of another tool for decision-making on environmental policies.

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